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THEORETICAL SOURCES OF TEXT PRAGMALINGUISTIC ANALYSIS

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Abstract. this article deals with the theories of text and pragmalinguistic analysis. In addition, author provides notions concerning pragmalinguistic and tex analysis as well as compares western scholar's views and domestic linguists who contributed in the sphere of comparative linguistics.

Keywords: pragmalinguistics, addressee, addresser, intralinguistics, extralinguistics, explicit, implicit.

Nowadays, in addition to traditional grammatical, semantic, and methodological analyzes, the text is analyzed from the linguopoetic, psycholinguistic, sociolinguistic, cognitive, linguocultural, discursive, and pragmalinguistic points of view. Text is considered the main object in computer linguistics and automatic translation. This, of course, is the result of the integration of disciplines, at the same time, it can be said that the approach to text analysis based on modern trends and principles of linguistics expands the territory of linguistic research in all ways, sheds light on the speech capabilities, social, cultural essence, intellectual-cognitive, spiritual, ethnic characteristics of language units.

As a branch of modern linguistics, pragmalinguistics pays particular attention to the issue of human speech activity, the process of engaging in mutual communication, and the combination of linguistic and non-linguistic factors acting in this process. Since the main part of human activity consists of communicative relations and determines the way of life of people, the text is considered the main tool that acts as a formative tool of communication and interaction. Communication and text are interconnected and require each other. In addition, the text is not only a unit of speech communication, but also a unit of communicative relations in general. If we analyze the speech text of a certain person, we recognize that it was first of all expressed by the communicator (addressee), which was transmitted to another communicator (addresser). The fact that the transmitted information is formed on the basis of certain laws of the language (intralinguistics) means that it meets the requirements of the text, and in the transmission of information from the addresser to the addressee, the mutual relations of the communicants (extralinguistics) are of great importance [1].

“Pragmatics” (from the Greek pragma - work, action) is actually a philosophical concept, which was used even before Socrates, and later philosophers such as J. Locke and

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E. Kant adopted it from Aristotle. In this way, the stream of pragmatism arose in philosophy. The main period of development of this current is the 19th-20th centuries. Especially in the 20s and 30s of the 20th century, the widespread promotion of the ideas of pragmatism began to be clearly felt. The services of C. Peirce, R. Carnap, C. Morris, and L. Wittgenstein should be noted in the wide spread of this propaganda in America and Europe [2].

In pragmalinguistics, on the one hand, the pragmatic possibilities of language units are analyzed, on the other hand, attention is paid to the issue of achieving pragmatic competence in the speech process, on the third hand, the semantic and pragmatic features of speech acts, the expression of meaning, the mechanism of speech influence are analyzed, and fourth, the speech related to the national mentality language units specific to manners are studied, fifthly, the issue of linguistic realization of the evaluation category specific to the modal aspect of expression is also included in the pragmalinguistic studies.

Researches of the American philosopher and linguist J. Searle are of great importance in the development of theories of pragmalinguistics. The scientist puts forward valid opinions on the issue of the theory and classification of the speech act, the differences between the illocutionary and propositional contents of the speech act [3]. J. Searle's research still serves as an important theoretical source for the semantic and pragmatic structure of expression and the classification of speech acts.

In modern Russian linguistics, A. Maslova is known for her research on the directions of the anthropocentric paradigm: linguistics, cognitive linguistics, intercultural communication, and the theory of speech influence. One of the theoretical sources of our research is the scholar's textbook "Vvedenie v pragmalingvistiku" ("Introduction to Pragmalinguistics"), which covers the main principles and concepts of this field in depth. A. Maslova, the role of pragmalinguistics in the anthropocentric paradigm, the importance of this paradigm in today's development of linguistics, the theory, structure and classification of speech act, indirect speech act, specific aspects of pragmalinguistic analysis, speech situation, communicative strategy and communicative tactics, types of communication, principles and postulates, sheds light on the core issues of pragmalinguistics, such as communicative failure, proves it by means of examples taken from literary texts, scientifically substantiates the fundamental essence of pragmalinguistics and its place in the system of sciences [4].

The first observations of pragmalinguistics in Uzbek linguistics were aimed at studying the phenomenon of presupposition, and N. Mahmudov, A. Nurmonov published the first scientific articles on this subject [5]. U. Rahimov studied the presupposition of loadings in a monographic plan and started extensive research in this field [6]. The famous linguist, professor A. Nurmonov continued his views on the field of pragmalinguistics, and

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as the research object of the field, non-descriptive words in the sentence, words connecting the content of the sentence with the speaker, introductions expressing the direct mode, words and tools expressing evaluation, discourse reflecting the subjective psyche of a person, notes the issues of speech habit (etiquette), means of expressing respect, and presupposition [7].

In the 90s of the 20th century, the weight of scientific research devoted to the analysis of pragmatic aspects in the speech realization of linguistic units began to increase in Uzbek linguistics. In particular, the connotative function of language units, which are considered important issues of pragmalinguistics, are M. Mamadaliyeva, [8] the impact function of the text, the importance of laughter-inducing means in creating a text with a target meaning Sh. It was studied by Abdurahmonov in a monographic plan [9]. In E. Ibragimova's candidate's dissertation, it was shown that pragmatics “as a new field of linguistics is related to the issue of the context of the speech situation that serves to realize the main communicative intention of the participants of this process” and that it is an object of stylistic-linguopragmatics [10].

Pragmalinguistics studies the process of communication, the combination of linguistic and non-linguistic factors in this process, the expression of communication units, their impact, the expression of the assessment category related to the person and communication in the text, and the effectiveness of language units in this regard. Pragmatic functions of language units are fully reflected, especially in the process of live communication, surrounded by various speech situations and types of communication behavior. It is for this reason that issues such as speech communication and its stages, communication behavior, types of speech ethics are considered important issues of pragmalinguistics. Professor S. Mominov's doctoral dissertation contains in-depth observations and analyzes of these issues. In particular, the information presented in the first chapter of the dissertation on the elements of communication, types, behavior of communication, compositional stages of communication can serve as a theoretical basis for pragmalinguistic analysis. Considerations about the stages of the addressee's activity are especially important in researching the communication process. It is absolutely impossible to study the problem of communication behavior without taking into account the national character - the specific customs, values and traditions of the people of the nation. Because communication behavior is an integral part of a nation's character, and they are closely related to each other.

Today, pragmalinguistics has formed as a separate field in our linguistics. Professor Sh. Safarov's research in this process is particularly noteworthy. In the study guide “Pragmalinguistics”, the scientist reflects on the formation, development and prospects of this field, and emphasizes that the study of the pragmatic features of linguistic activity and the factors that create these features is important for determining the social nature of the

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language. In this study guide, the formation of the communicative-pragmatic direction, the priority of pragmatics in the linguistic-semiotic system, the subject of pragmalinguistics, the theory of the speech act, the relationship between semantics and pragmatics, the events that form pragmatic content, the principles and rules of effective communication, deixis and the text of speech communication, the structure of discourse and its analysis problems are theoretically justified by comparing a number of sources related to world pragmalinguistics. It is shown that the main methodological idea defining the principles of pragmatic analysis is the activity theory [11].

The pragmatic features of the text in Uzbek linguistics were researched by professor M. Hakimov literally in a monographic plan. In the dissertation, it is noted that the pragmatic aspect of linguistic research is connected with the subject of speech, all speech expressions related to the person and his mental state, the individual style of the author of the speech that is, the intention of how to express the thought, are considered the object of pragmatic research. Lingvopragmatic analysis showed that it includes such meanings as joy, bitterness, surprise, surprise, objection, command, request, boasting, disdain, sarcasm, and rudeness [12]. In M. Hakimov's doctoral dissertation, the terms phonopragmatics, lexopragmatics, morphopragmatics, pragmatic syntax were used for the first time in Uzbek linguistics. The text was studied on the basis of the principles of linguistic pragmatics and the theory of the speech act, the specific laws of the contents expressed in open and hidden (explicit and implicit) forms were shown, the rules regarding their semantic, syntactic, presuppositional and pragmatic features were clarified.

In recent years, as in world linguistics, in Uzbek linguistics, the number of researches on the interpretation of pragmatic features of language units has increased. In particular, the issue of categories forming the pragmatic content of the text is discussed by prof. It was studied by S. Boymirzayeva in a monographic plan. In this dissertation, special attention is paid to the fact that the text is the unity of information exchange and that it mainly serves to fulfill this task, therefore, its content requires the coordination of tasks such as communication and information exchange, and the compatibility of the denotative part of the text with the communicative purpose and the pragmatic purpose. Understanding the text, the role and types of modality category in its communicative-pragmatic content are covered in depth on the basis of examples from Uzbek artistic texts [36].

The pragmalinguistic approach to the text is still relevant today. In world and Uzbek linguistics, scientific articles and manuals have been created on various issues of this field, and this process continues. Pragmalinguistics is especially important in the fields of translation studies, computer linguistics, automatic text translation, and language education, which shows the promising and practical aspects of this field.

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